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AN ANALYSIS OF NOUNS AND VERBS USED IN SELECTED ONLINE FABLES

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Abstract

This study analyzed parts of speech found in forty Aesop's fables with specific attention to the categories and frequencies of nouns and verbs used. This study aimed to analyze the most used of nouns and verbs in the stories. The material used in the forty selected Aesop's fable from the website entitled <http://www.bbc.co.uk>. An analysis of the types of words was done using the program entitled <https://open.xerox.com> as an instrument for collecting data. The statistics used in data collection was percentage. The results of the study showed that there were two types of nouns and two types of verb in the selected Aesop fables. "Common Nouns" was the most commonly used with a frequency of 95.47%, and "action verbs" were the most commonly used with a frequency of 83.62%. Furthermore, "gerund" was also found in these Aesop fables. Comprehending types of words will help strengthen reading efficiency, reduce confusion of words usage as well as for readers to fully enjoy reading.

Keywords: Online Fables; Aesop Fables; Parts of Speech; Noun Usage; Verb Usage.

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1. Introduction

Education is the process of learning for the growth of the prosperity of the people in society. That is accomplished through teaching, practicing, training and cultural inheritance, academic progress creativity, knowledge constructing which arise from the environment, society, learning and supporting factors throughout a person's lifetime (Thailand Education Act of B.E. 2542, 1999). Therefore, education is an important instrument for developing people for globalization through the process of learning, teaching, and technology. Language is a means of communication and connection all around the world, and English is regarded as a language that is used on the internet by most of the people in the world and the fourth most spoken (Internet World Users by Language, 2010). As we know that we are living in the world of globalization. English language is a common language and is spoken in many countries. It is considered a

universal language. Most of the universities worldwide include English as one of their major subject (Importance of English language, 2011).

In the year 2015, Thailand is stepping into ASEAN for which the formal language is English (Importance of English in ASEAN, n.d). This means that English will be used for communication, interaction with government officials, as well as volunteers and organizations that are concerned with the government and also the private sector. Therefore, not only will the government's officials be using English but also the general population as well. For business or trading, people will be able to travel across borders for job opportunities, travelling, or education. For this reason, English is the foremost instrument for communicating between the citizens of ASEAN in the modern day borderless and competitive world. Thus, the government has assigned it to be the second language in every curriculum of all grades, including adult education.

Reading is one of the main factors for Thai people to improve their level of education so that English can be comparable to the standard of international education. The differences between reading and watching television are vast because reading is a mental process, the brain has to analyze data, recognize words linking vocabulary meaning by understanding context of the words in the original sentence. When a student reads and comprehends literature, this helps their concentration, discipline, and creativity.

There are many benefits of reading. Firstly, reading improves vocabulary; the meaning of one word can be understood by reading the context of the other words in the sentence. Secondly, it gives a glimpse into other cultures and places of the world: provides an insight into the diversity of people, their customs, their lifestyles and much, much more. You become more aware of different places and gain on understanding into how and why other people live their lives the way they do. This improves concentration and focus and builds self-esteem: The more one reads, the more knowledgeable one becomes. So it's a chain reaction. Furthermore, reading improves memory: Many studies show that if you do not use your memory, you lose it. Reading helps stretch memory muscles because it requires remembering details, facts and figures and in literature, plot lines, themes, and characters (Divya, 2008).

Parts of speech are the main interests of this time study, which can be said that it is the most important basic part of languages. Parts of speech are very important in sentences especially in reading and writing composition, how each word is related and how it plays its role in the sentence. Some words have similar grammatical properties and sometimes even morphology. In English parts of speech are listed by noun, verb, adjective, adverb, pronoun, preposition, conjunction, interjection as well as articles. Noun and verb are the main focus on this research. Analyzing these 2 confusing parts of speech can provide a better understanding in reading and can build better writing skills.

The better we understand parts of speech, the better we understand reading. By knowing the role of each word in the sentence, we can prevent the confusion and misunderstanding. As mentioned above, some words get similar grammatical properties and morphology, for children with less experience in reading, it is a good way to provide them this source of knowledge. In this study, researcher will use 40 fables to analysis parts of speech (nouns and verbs), which will be an easy

method for the students to understand the very basic part of language and be able to adapt it for the future advanced writing and reading.

The researcher sought documentation and research about reading strategies' and found that the teachers have to teach reading as a process and choose the appropriate text for students. The researcher is interested in reading to improve reading skill. Reading fables can encourage the students to use their prior knowledge. The teaching of reading fables begin with the prior knowledge, and then follows what the students want to know, and then learn and finally conclude by identifying the type of parts of speech.

Statement of the Problem

In every language there are four important basic skills which are listening, speaking, reading, and writing. All these basic skills are used everywhere in daily communication, from schools to workplaces. It can be said that among all these four skills, reading is one of the most difficult skills of learning. If learners have more skills in reading, they would have good background on parts of speech. Teachers can also provide materials and encourage them to be more attracted to books that will support their reading ability and keep them moving ahead with reading. Reading can provide a million sources of knowledge and can give a better vision as they explore the world without going anywhere. An important part of reading is to understand the words and its role in the sentence and then one can fully understand the whole context. Understanding parts of speech can prevent misunderstanding of similar words and their function. Good basic skill in reading can provide the ability to comprehend future complicated reading as well as provide correct grammar in terms of writing. The above-mentioned messages are the rationale why the researcher is interested in studying this, not only to comprehend in reading but in writing as well.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to analyze noun and verb used from selected online Aesop's fable

Scope of the Study

The study mainly focused on parts of speech analysis, which will focus on noun and verb used from forty Aesop's fable only. The stories were taken from BBC http://www.bbc.co.uk/learning/schoolradio/subjects/english/aesops_fables.

Significance of the Study

Reading is essential to educational success. Good reading skills are the basis for all levels of understanding. Reading skills have an effect on student's ability to comprehend, think critically, and express thoughts and opinions orally and in writing. When students are unable to read, they are also unable to understand and be effective communicators. Mraz and Rasinski (2006) stated that: the more students read, the better readers they become. This study emphasizes on the parts of speech analysis of nouns and verbs. It demonstrates the roles of the words in the sentences, that same words can play a different role if placed differently in the sentences. This study can be very useful for better understanding in reading and prevent the confusion of same words with

different roles in the sentence. Parts of speech may provide a further skill in advanced writing by fully understand in it. This can be a preliminary study for students to start learning English through a linguistic approach which provides a basic understanding of languages (Allington, 1988).

2. Materials and Methods

The study analyzed the forty Aesop's Fable, which were download from the website http://www.bbc.co.uk/learning/schoolradio/subjects/english/aesops_fables. Analysis can be made by a setting in the tool according to the input. The aims were to analyze types of noun and verbs.

Research Design

The research design was the one group design. Before the analysis, parts of speech were categorized according to the types of nouns and verbs. There are two main types of nouns; Common Noun, Proper Noun. The Verbs were categorized in two types; Action Verbs, Linking Verbs. After that, checklist the frequency of each type of noun and verb by using the website, <https://open.xerox.com> and collected data.

Research Instruments

The Instruments will consist of the 40 stories from Aesop' Fables, from the website www.bbc.co.uk/learning/schoolradio/subjects/english/aesops_fable. The data are processed and assessed by the website, 'This tool assigns a part of speech (POS) tag to each word of the input text. Tags are language specific and available in the Part of speech tag sets page. The content analysis was both qualitative and quantitative to find out how many nouns and verbs used in Aesop's fables.

Construction and Efficiency of the Instrument

The construction consisted of the 40 stories from Aesop' Fables. Nouns and Verbs are mainly considered. The Nouns were categorized in two main types; Common Noun, Proper Noun. The Verbs were categorized in two types: Action Verbs and Linking Verbs. The program checked the frequency, summarized and found the percentage according to the types of nouns and verbs used.

Data collection

The data was drawn from 40 stories from Aesop' Fables, and collected by analyzed through the story by the website [https://open.xerox.com/Services/fst-nlp-tools/Consume/Part% 20of% 20Speech% 20Tagging% 20\(Standard\)-178](https://open.xerox.com/Services/fst-nlp-tools/Consume/Part%20of%20Speech%20Tagging%20(Standard)-178). It categorized the types of nouns and verbs, and listed the frequency, according to the types of nouns and verbs.

Data Analysis

An analysis based on the study of checklist was discussed by 1- 40 stories. The checklist items started from nouns namely, the Common Noun and Proper Noun and continued to the verbs

namely the Action Verbs and Linking Verbs. The findings of this study were mainly based on the analysis of nouns and verbs, specifically on the frequency of nouns and verbs found in the forty fables.

3. Results and Discussions

This chapter presents the quantitative results of the study showing the frequency and percentage of the nouns and verbs used in 40 Aesop's Fables. This is the presentation of the result. The following are the titles of the stories.

The Hare and the Tortoise	The Frog and the Ox
The Fox and the Crow	The Monkey as King
The Bundle of the Sticks	The Gnat and the Lion
The North wind and the Sun	The Fox and the Grapes
The Dog, Cockerel and the Fox	The Miller, his Son and the Donkey
The Wolf and the Heron	The Donkey in the Lion' Skin
The Gnat and the Grasshopper	The Vain and the Grasshopper
The Frog Who Wanted a King	The Cat and the Mice
The Lion and the Mouse	The Caged Bird and the Bat
The Fox and the Goat	The Lion and the Elephant
The Crow and the Pitcher	The Fox and the Stork
Two Travelers and the Bear	The Goose that Laid the Golden Eggs
The Kid and the Wolf	The Old Lion and the Fox
The Eagle and the Jackdaw	The Wolf in Sheep's Clothing
The Goatherd and the Wild Goat	The Dog in the Manger
Androcles and the Lion	The Dog and the Reflection
The Heron and the Fish	The Eagle and the Tortoise
The Town Mouse and the Country Mouse	Belling the Cat
The Too Fat Fox	The Rat and the Elephant
The Ant and the Dove	The Boy Who Cried Wolf

Results of the Study

This section presents results of the study toward the frequency of nouns and verbs from selected stories.

Table 1: Categories, Frequencies, and Percentage of Nuns Used.

	<u>Types of nouns</u>	<u>Frequencies</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
1	Common Nouns	2,086	95.47
2	Proper Nouns	99	4.53
	Total	2,185	100

The table compares two types of nouns which were used differently in 40 fables: Common Noun and Proper Noun.

These two types of nouns used in the 40 fables are ordered from the greatest frequency to the least namely, 1) Common Noun and 2) Proper Noun respectively.

The table indicates that the most number of words found in the stories are Common Nouns found are 95.47 %. Proper Noun found with 4.53 %. The total number of nouns is 2,185 words.

Table 2: Categories, Frequency and Percentage of Verbs Used

	<u>Types of nouns</u>	<u>Frequencies</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
1	Action Verbs	2,145	83.62
2	Linking Verbs	420	13.38
	Total	2,565	100

The table above gives information about how many verbs are used in 40 stories through three types of verbs. Overall, it can be seen that, there are two types of verbs used with a total of 3,342 words. Action verbs used most with 73.61 % while linking verbs has the smallest verb used with 4.31 %. In addition, the study found that not only two types of nouns and two types of verbs but also gerunds were found in 40 Aesop's fables.

Discussions

The Aesop's fables use simple nouns and verbs so that all level of learners can read and understand easily. Fables are a type of traditional literature that are believed to have originated over a thousand years ago with Aesop. Characters in fables are often animals that behave and talk like humans. The moral of a fable helps us to understand the human experience and lessons about life. After analyzing the 40 fables, the results of the study found that each story contained two main types of nouns and two types of verbs. "Nouns are simply the names we give to everything around us, whether it be a person, an event, a place or an object, etc. Every particular name used to define something is a noun. E.g.: Amsterdam, Anita, Blackberry, Honesty, Waiter, etc.". There are several ways to classify the types of nouns that exist in the English language. In traditional grammar, nouns are taught to be words that refer to people, places, things, or abstract ideas. While modern linguistics find this definition to be problematic because it relies on non-specific nouns such as thing to specifically define what a noun is, much of our social understanding of what nouns are defers to the traditional definition. The different types of Nouns are "Common nouns are words that are used to refer or call people or animals, or objects in general, e.g. men, women, male, female, lands, countries, bridge, animals, eagerness, playfulness." Most common nouns that are found in Aesop's Fables are also normally found in general. They are words that refer to people, animals and objects. Because the events in the fables take place in the daily life of local people in accordance with the circumstances around, and the characters in the tales are also easily found in the area. Therefore vocabulary in these stories are mostly common nouns, which are the words referred to people, animals, or objects, both in singular and plural forms such as: The following are sample sentences which appear in the stories. 'Look at me!' said the *Hare* to the other *animals*. Just look how fast I can run.' (The hare and the tortoise.) Hare: *Hare* is a common noun used to refer to animals that are easily found in the local area. Animals: *Animals* is a common noun in plural form used to refer to animals in general. She had 247 *children*, and it is hard to remember that many *names*, so she called everyone stanley to give her *memory* a rest (The fox and the ox). Children: *Children* is a

noun in plural form used to refer to many kids. Names: *Names* is a noun in plural form used to refer to a lot of different names. Memory: *Memory* is a noun in singular form used to refer to memories of people and is spoken in general. “Proper nouns are words that identifies a person, place, or thing in particular, e.g. Frank, Canada, Rama 9 Bridge, Bangkok, and Sunday. In written English, proper nouns begin with capital letters.”

These types of noun are few words found in each story in Aesop’s fable compared to common nouns. However, there are 5 stories which are not found proper nouns used. That is because most of the characters are animals, but behave and talk like human; therefore they are the main characters of the stories. Subsequently vocabulary that is used to call or refer to people is not commonly found. There are 28 stories in which names of people or places are not found, as shown in the following sentences: Mrs Mckenzie had six strong sons. They were Peter, Paul and Patrick, Philip, Frankie and Fred (The bundle of the sticks). 'You're Stanley, aren't you?' 'No mum, I'm Zebadee.'” (The fox and the ox). *Mrs. Mckenzie , Peter, Paul ,Patrick, Philip, Frankie and Fred, Stanley and Zebadee* are the proper name that used as the names of people who appeared in the story.'I love ch...ch...Cheese!' whined Mini-Mouse, hungrily. 'So do I!' squeaked Mildred-Mouse. *Mini-Mouse and Mildred-Mouse* are the proper name that used as the names of people but they are animal which characters in this story are animals, behave and talk like human who appeared in the story. “Verbs are the most important component of any sentence. These words talk about the action or the state of any noun or subject. This means that verbs show what the subject is doing or what is the state or situation of the subject.”

Action verbs are verbs that describe actions and things taking place rather than states. This type of verb is the most commonly found of all verbs, as they are verbs that describe actions of subjects or characters in the sentences and in the stories. They allowed us to understand the conditions of each character, to what they are doing, and how the stories would proceed. In addition, they help enhancing the clarity of the stories, and also make them funnier and more appealing. But as fable are matter of story-telling, most of actions verbs that are found in Aesop’s Fables are in past simple verb forms, as shown in the following sentences: The fox *stopped* at last, hot and panting (The Fox and the Grapes). They *talked* and *laughed* as they *strode* along (Two travelers and the bear). *Stopped, talked, laughed* and *strode* those were appeared in the stories are in past simple forms and also describe action the subject. Linking verbs are verbs that link a subject with an adjective or noun that describes or identifies the subject.

Table 3: List of linking verb

linking verb	linking verb	linking verb	linking verb
act	acted	am	appear
appeared	to be are	are	being be
became	become	can be	come
could be	could have come	did	do
has become	has been	has seemed	have
felt	get	go	got
grew	grow	had	had become
had been	had seemed	has	has appeared
have appeared	have become	have been	have seemed

indicate	is	is being	is getting
keep	look	looked	may be
might be might	have been	must	prove
remain	remained	seem	seemed
seeming	seems	shall be	shall have been
should be	should have appeared	should have been	smell
sound	stay	stayed	taste
tasted	turn	was	was being
wax	waxed	went	were
will be	will become	will have become	will have been
will seem	would be		

(www.yourdictionary.com)

The table above showed the list of linking verbs. These types of verbs are not usually found in Aesop's Fables, as they are verbs that connect actions of subjects or characters in the stories. They are also used to clarify the meaning of each sentence, to make them more appealing and describe the past events, as shown in the following sentences: The new cat didn't look old...or lazy. This cat *looked* young and keen and hungry (Belling the Cat). Before him lay the Roaring River – as vast as a sea, or so it *seemed* to tiny Ant (The Ant and the Dove). Fergus Fowler and he *had* locked her in a cage outside his cottage window (The Caged Bird and the Bat). 'The gerund looks exactly the same as a present participle, but it is useful to understand the difference between the two. The gerund always has the same function as a noun (although it looks like a verb. George (1980) states that gerund is the - ing form of the verb used as a noun, gerund has the same form as the present participle. However, it functions differently in the sentence, it is always can function in any noun position.'" This study also focused on 4 types of gerunds and the example of the gerunds used. These are following: The gerund as the subject of the sentence. The gerund as the object of the sentence using as objective of verb. The gerund as the object of preposition. The gerund as the Subjective complement. The gerund as the appositive.

4. Conclusions & Recommendations

The purpose of this study was to analyze noun and verb used from selected online Aesop's fable. The study mainly focused on parts of speech analysis, which will focus on noun and verb used from forty Aesop's fable only. The stories were taken from BBC http://www.bbc.co.uk/learning/schoolradio/subjects/english/aesops_fables. The study analyzed the forty Aesop's Fable, which were download from the website http://www.bbc.co.uk/learning/schoolradio/subjects/english/aesops_fables. Analysis can be made by a setting in the tool according to the input. The aims were to analyze types of noun and verbs.

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speech (POS) tag to each word of the input text. Tags are language specific and available in the Part of speech tag sets page. The content analysis was both qualitative and quantitative to find out how many nouns and verbs used in Aesop's fables. The construction consisted of the 40 stories from Aesop' Fables. Nouns and Verbs are mainly considered. The Nouns were categorized in two main types; Common Noun, Proper Noun. The Verbs were categorized in two types: Action Verbs and Linking Verbs. The program checked the frequency, summarized and found the percentage according to the types of nouns and verbs used. The data was drawn from 40 stories from Aesop' Fables, and collected by analyzed through the story by the website [https://open.xerox.com/Services/fst-nlp-tools/Consume/Part%20of%20Speech%20Tagging%20\(Standard\)-178](https://open.xerox.com/Services/fst-nlp-tools/Consume/Part%20of%20Speech%20Tagging%20(Standard)-178). It categorized the types of nouns and verbs, and listed the frequency, according to the types of nouns and verbs. An analysis based on the study of checklist was discussed by 1- 40 stories. The checklist items started from nouns namely, the Common Noun and Proper Noun and continued to the verbs namely the Action Verbs and Linking Verbs. The findings of this study were mainly based on the analysis of nouns and verbs, specifically on the frequency of nouns and verbs found in the forty fables.

Results of the study showed that there were 2 types of nouns and 2 types of verbs used in the 40 fables; common noun and proper noun. There were 2 types of verbs; action verbs and linking verbs. Furthermore, based on the findings of this study, there were gerunds used in the 40 fables mentioned. The types and the frequency of nouns used in the 40 stories of Aesop's fables are Common Noun (95.47%) and Proper Noun (4.53%). The types and the frequency of verbs used in the 40 stories of Aesop's fables are Action Verbs (83.62%) and Linking Verbs (13.38%).

Recommendations

For the researcher, it is recommended to also use other stories to analyze nouns and verbs used and also using other parts of speech such as adjectives, adverbs, preposition, conjunction, and interjection.

For young readers, it is recommended that young readers can read and choose their favorite stories from these 40 Fables. Also, it is better if they can identify at least some, if not all, nouns and verbs in the stories. Like the names of the characters of the stories, places, events, things, and ideas.

For Primary Teachers, it is recommended that Primary teachers must know how to identify nouns as well as verbs so they can explain well to their students. This study can help motivate primary teachers to read more and can help identify nouns as well as verbs through concrete examples from the fables. The results of this study helped enhance and develop quality reading practices that will lead to achieving measurable reading outcomes.

For Future Researchers, the results of this study can guide researchers for future study such as identifying nouns and verbs as well as gerunds and participles using other stories. This study can also give base information on how to identify nouns and verbs, as well as gerunds in 40 Fables.

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